

EFFECTIVENESS OF LIFE SKILL INTERVENTIONAL PROGRAMME IN ENHANCING LIFE SKILLS OF B.ED NORMAL AND SPECIAL EDUCATION STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract:

The aim of this study was to enhance the life skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers through life skills interventional programme with particular focus to decision making skill. Decision making helps us to deal constructively with decisions in our lives. Making a decision involves making a commitment; however small, rationally and emotionally. The study was conducted on a sample of 60 B.Ed. special education student teachers to assess the effectiveness of interventional programme on decision making skills. Life skill questionnaire with decision making skill was constructed and standardized. Module on decision making skill was prepared with objectives, activities, story and importance of decision making skill. The study reveals that (1) there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers; (2) There is significant difference between the posttest scores of the control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers; (3) There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of control group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers; (4) There is significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of experimental group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers.

Introduction:

"Truly successful decision-making relies on a balance between deliberate and instinctive thinking" says Malcolm Gladwell. Decision making helps us to deal constructively in making decisions in our lives and it can have consequences on our health (Mettas, A. 2011). It can teach people how to actively make decisions about their actions in relation to healthy assessment of different options and what effects these different decisions are likely to have.

Review of Related Literature:

Conducting the life skill programme was emotionally and professionally satisfying revealed the investigation on adolescent's life skills education programme based on the experience at Bangalore by Galagali (2010). The study of Jayachitra (2015) aimed at finding the relationship between life skills of B.Ed. students and their teaching performance revealed that teaching performance can be predicted by each correlates of life skill either separately or collectively and recommended that teacher education programmes must include an intensive exposure to life skills.

Decision Making Process:

"Stay committed to your decisions, but stay flexible in your approach" says Tom Robbins. The steps involved in decision making process are as follows: 1. Defining the problem, 2. Gathering information and resources, 3. Listing the options, 4. Weighing and comparing options, 5. Making decision, 6. Making a plan of action, and 7. Evaluating the decision (Nair, R. 2010).

Need and Significance of the Study:

Today one of the most important criteria for success in the education field is the ability to take decisions in right time. This study will help the student teachers to get the knowledge of decision making skills, through which they can solve their own problems by selecting one course of action from several possible alternatives. In everyday life, we often have to make decisions fast, without enough time to systematically go through the above action and thinking steps. In such situations the most effective decision making strategy is to keep an eye on our goals and then let our intuition suggest the right choice. Ultimately, this study will help them to develop the decision making skills to actively make decisions about their actions in relation to healthy assessment of different options and, what effects these different decisions are likely to have.

Statement of the Problem:

In the present investigation, the investigator intends to develop module for decision making skills through experimental study in order to enhance the decision making skills of the B.Ed. special education student teachers. Hence the problem for the present study is stated as follows: Effectiveness of life skills interventional program in enhancing life skills among B.Ed. special education and normal education student teachers.

Objectives:

- ✓ To help the student teachers to understand the meaning of decision making.

- ✓ To help the student teachers to understand the importance of decision making.
- ✓ To help the student teachers to make better decisions.
- ✓ To develop a module on decision making skills.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference in decision making skills among the student teachers before and after the interventional program.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between the pretest scores of control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the posttest scores of control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of control group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of experimental group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.

Methodology:

The investigator adapted experimental method as the study was experimental in nature. Experimentation is the name given to the type of educational research in which the investigator controls the educative factors to which a student or group of students are subjected during the period of enquiry and observes the resulting achievement. In this study, the investigator adapted quasi-experimental design i.e. non-equivalent pre-test post-test design.

Sample:

The investigator selected the B.Ed. student teachers as ideal subject for studying the effectiveness of interventional programme on life skills. The sample for the study was 60 student teachers who have joined for B.Ed. special education course in Dr. MGR Institute of Special Education and Research, Chennai, India. The Investigator divided the 60 students into two groups by matched pair procedure. One group was taken as control group and another group as experimental group.

Construction and Standardization of Life Skill Questionnaire:

To assess the effectiveness of interventional programme among student teachers, after reviewing many related studies done in the field of life skills, the following 10 life skills were selected for the scale. They were 1. Critical thinking, 2. Decision making, 3. Problem solving, 4. Effective communication, 5. Coping with stress, 6. Coping with emotion, 7. Self-awareness, 8. Empathy, 9. Interpersonal relationship and 10. Creative thinking.

Type of Test Items:

On the basis of the objectives and the areas to be covered, life skills scale was constructed by making use of Likert's method of summation to get a five point judgment on each item. Every item is in the statement form. Five response categories are provided for responding to every item. These response categories are Not at All, Rarely, Sometimes, Often, and Very Often. In these response categories, the subject is required to select the most appropriate response category indicating her/his attitude.

Pre-Try Out of Scale:

After preparing scale, it was given along with its objectives to subject experts and judges including professors of educational field. After listening to their arguments and suggestions, some questions were deleted and some were reframed. Thus questions were reduced from 150 to 100.

Pilot Study:

The pilot study is meant to help the investigator to find out the difficulty of the respondents in understanding the test items. It helps us to find out the vague and irrelevant statements if any. To try out the items, a preliminary form of the questionnaire was prepared. After constructing the life skills questionnaire, a pilot study was conducted on a random sample of 25 B.Ed. student teachers. The pilot study was conducted with a view to find out the reliability and validity of the tools and also to eliminate any ambiguity so that students do not feel any difficulty in responding to the items on the scale. Scoring was done on five point scale. Total scores for each subject were calculated which represented the individual total score.

Scoring:

The procedure of scoring the test was quite simple. Scoring was done with the help of five-point Likert type scale. The marks were given to response as 1 for 'Not at all', 2 for 'Rarely', 3 for 'Sometimes', 4 for 'Often', and 5 for 'Very often' for positive questions in the normal order and for negative questions the marks were given in the reverse order as 5 for 'Not at all', 4 for 'Rarely', 3 for 'Sometimes', 2 for 'Often', and 1 for 'Very often'. The total of these scores was the final score of an individual. The scores in the final scale ranged from 100 to 500.

Item Analysis:

In the method of summated ratings, rejection or selection of statements is done on the basis of item analysis. For this, the frequency distribution of scores based upon the responses to all statements was considered. To ascertain whether the item differentiate between high and low group, the t-value between two

groups of each item was found out by analyzing the responses of the 27% of the subjects with the highest total scores i.e. high group and also of the 27% of the subjects with the lowest total scores. The t-value for evaluating the responses of high and low groups to the individual statements was found out. All the items were found to have significant t-values, hence it was retained. The items were then arranged in the rank order according to their t-values.

Reliability:

Reliability can be defined as proportion of the variability in a set of test scores. Coefficient of reliability was determined by the split-half method (even-odd). The scale was divided into two equal halves. Items with odd numbers formed one half test and items with even numbers formed second half test. For this purpose, the test was administered to a sample of 25 student teachers randomly selected in Stella Matutina College of Education. The correlation coefficient was calculated. The reliability coefficient by Spearman-Brown Prophecy came out to be 0.84, which indicated high reliability of test.

Validity:

In the present scale, face validity and content validity were ensured. These were ensured when the authorities agreed that the questions afford adequate coverage of particular area and unanimous agreement of various subject experts including professors of educational psychology, careful analysis of instructional objectives, and the actual subject matter studied. Also the index of reliability is taken as a measure of validity (Garret, 1969). The validity was established through reliability i.e., by \sqrt{r} . The square root of reliability was computed as 0.91, which showed the test was found to be significantly valid.

Procedure and Data Gathering:

The pretest was conducted among both control group as well as experimental group students. The performance of control group and the experimental group students was more or less the same. Experimental treatment was given to the experimental group. An ordinary treatment was given to the control group. A post test was conducted among both the groups of students. The students of experimental groups were able to score better than the students of control group in the post test. Thus the effectiveness of life skill interventional program in enhancing decision making skills was established.

Statistical Techniques Used:

Differential analysis method was used for data analysis. It provided inferences involving determination of statistical significance of difference between groups with reference to selected variables. Mean, standard deviation and 't' test were used for this purpose.

Analysis of Data:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the pretest scores of control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.

Table 1: Difference between the Pretest Scores of Control Group and Experimental Group with Respect to their Decision Making Skill

S.No	Group	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degrees of Freedom	p Value	Remarks at 0.05 level
1	Control-Pre test	30	26.5	4.924	58	0.162	Not Significant
2	Experimental-Pre test	30	24.46	6.796			

The above table shows that the mean scores of control group pretest with respect to their decision making skills is 26.5 with standard deviation of 4.924 while the mean scores of experimental group pretest with respect to their decision making skills is 24.46 with standard deviation of 6.79. Here the 'p' value is 0.162, which is more than the 'p' value at 95% confidence level (0.05) at degrees of freedom of 58. That is $0.162 > 0.05$. The hypothesis which assumed no difference in the pretest scores of control and experimental group with respect to their decision making skills is accepted. Hence we conclude that there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skills.

Figure 1: Mean Scores of Pre Test of Control Group and Experimental Group

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the posttest scores of control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.

Table 2: Difference between the mean posttest scores of control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skill

S.No	Group	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degrees of Freedom	p Value	Remarks at 0.05 level
1	Control-Pre test	30	26.6	5.123	58	0.000	Significant
2	Experimental-Pre test	30	35.9	5.567			

The above table shows that the mean scores of the posttest of control group with respect to their decision making skills is 26.6 with standard deviation of 5.123 while the mean scores of the posttest of experimental group with respect to their decision making skills is 35.9 with standard deviation of 5.56. Here the 'p' value is 0.00, which is less than the 'p' value at 95% confidence level (0.05) with degrees of freedom of 58. That is $0.00 < 0.05$. The hypothesis which assumed no difference in the posttest scores of control and experimental group with respect to decision making skills is not accepted. Hence we conclude that there is significant difference between the posttest scores of the control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skills.

Figure 2: Mean Scores of Post Test of Control Group and Experimental Group

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of control group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.

Table 3: Difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of control group with respect to their decision making skill

S.No	Test	Number	Mean	SD	P Value	Remarks at 0.05 level
1	ControlPre test	30	26.5	4.92	0.918	Not Significant
2	Control Post test	30	26.6	5.12		

The above table shows that the mean scores of the pretest of control group with respect to their decision making skills is 26.5 with standard deviation of 4.92 while the mean scores of the posttest of control group with respect to their decision making skills is 26.6 with standard deviation of 5.12. Here the 'p' value is 0.918, which is greater than the 'p' value at 95% confidence level (0.05) with degrees of freedom of 58. That is $0.918 > 0.05$. The hypothesis which assumed no difference in the pretest and posttest scores of control group with respect to their decision making skills is accepted. Hence we conclude that there is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of control group with respect to their decision making skill.

Figure 3: Mean Scores of Pre Test and Post Test of Control Group

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of experimental group with respect to their decision making skill among B.Ed. special education student teachers.

Table 4: Difference between the Mean Pretest and Posttest Scores of Experimental Group with respect to their Decision Making Skill

S.No	Test	Number	Mean	SD	P Value	Remarks at 0.05 level
1	Experimental Pre test	30	24.46	6.796	0.000	Significant
2.	Experimental Post test	30	35.9	5.567		

The above table shows that the mean scores of the pretest of experimental group with respect to their decision making skills is 24.46 with standard deviation of 6.796 while the mean scores of the posttest of experimental group with respect to their decision making skills is 35.9 with standard deviation of 5.567. Here the 'p' value is 0.00, which is lesser than the 'p' value at 95% confidence level (0.05) with degrees of freedom of 58. That is $0.00 < 0.05$. The hypothesis which assumed no difference in the pretest and posttest scores of experimental group with respect to their decision making skills is not accepted. Hence we conclude that there is significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of experimental group with respect to their decision making skills.

Figure 4: Mean Scores of Pre Test and Post Test of Experimental Group

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers.
- ✓ There is significant difference between the posttest scores of the control group and experimental group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of control group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers.
- ✓ There is significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of experimental group with respect to their decision making skills among B.Ed. special education student teachers.

Educational Implications:

This study will help the student teachers to understand the importance of decision making skill and apply it effectively in diverse situation to cope with challenges of life. The ability to choose the right choice depending on the problem it has, is the matter of decision making. It is important to understand the process of individual decision making. When a situation comes to decide for an optional way then the individual must concentrate on the good decision rather than wavering. This study will help the student teachers to take good decisions in right time.

Suggestions for Further Research:

- ✓ This study was conducted with the sample of B.Ed. special education students who are doing their specialty in hearing impairment. The same study could be conducted with the B.Ed. special education students who are doing their specialty with other disabilities such as mental retardation, visual impairment, deaf blindness.
- ✓ The same study could be conducted with students who are enrolled in arts and science colleges.
- ✓ The same study could be conducted with engineering students.
- ✓ The study has been conducted in Chennai district; it can also be conducted in other districts.

Conclusion:

The major purpose of this study is to develop decision making skill among B.Ed special education student teachers. Decision making skill is the process of selecting a best course of action from among many alternatives. The student teachers can solve the problem in different ways on the basis of time and situation.

They will evaluate all the possible alternatives on the basis of situation and suitability. The selection of the best course of action is significant to bring smoothness in operation and achieve their goals in life.

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